

The dendrochronological dating of timbers from a ship found at Nøstodden, Norway.

Aoife Daly, Ph.d.

Dendro.dk report 15 : 2017

Commissioned by Jørgen Johannessen, Norsk Maritimt Museum

Three samples taken from a shipwreck at Nøstodden, Norway were submitted for analysis. All three are of *Quercus sp.*, oak. The samples contain 121, 154 and 164 tree-rings respectively. None of the samples have sapwood preserved. The tree-ring curves from two of the samples cross-match strongly, while the third cross-matches with these also, but with a less strong correlation (see table 1). An average of the two strongly matching tree-ring curves is calculated (Z179M001), of 169 rings in length, while a second average of all three, Z179M002, is also made, of 182 years. Initially, it was not possible to date this material dendrochronologically, using an extensive Northern European dataset for oak. Therefore, two sub-samples were extracted from sample 2, for C14 analysis. The results of this is reported previously (Daly 2016), suggesting that the timber for this ship was probably felled **after AD 1827-1945** (95,4 probability).

Given the very recent date of this material, the possibility that the wreck might be of American timber was suggested (Jørgen Johannessen pers comm). The measurements were therefore shared with colleagues in both Britain and USA, who carry out dendrochronological research into North American historic buildings. Dating for the Nøstodden material has succeeded, independently by three groups (Martin Bridge and Dan Miles pers comm, Ian Tyers pers comm and Carol Griggs pers comm).

The correlation between the average of the tree-ring curves from the three timbers from the wreck at the dated position AD 1651-1832 and diverse chronologies from North America is shown in table 2. Highly significant correlation (*t*-value) is achieved with a range of datasets, and the highest are with material from Virginia (VA), USA. This dating position is further supported by visual comparison of the average curve with a selection of North American chronologies (fig. 1).

		Z179001a	Z179002a	Z179003a
Average Z179M002	Z179001a	*	4,65	2,01
	Z179002a	4,65*		5,98
	Z179003a	2,01	5,98*	

Table 1. Nøstodden ship timbers. The correlation between the tree-ring curves from the oak samples from the ship. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

filenames			Z179M002	
	Start		AD 1651	
		End	AD 1832	
WVY	AD 1684	AD 1815	9.48	Walnut Valley Plantation, Surry County, VA
GLOx1	AD 1702	AD 1823	7.92	Gloucester Gaol & Tavern (Miles and Worthington in prep) VA
VA2008X	AD 932	AD 2005	7.32	Virginia Master Chronology (Worthington 2008)
VA021	AD 932	AD 1985	6.81	Blackwater River. bald cypress (<i>Taxodium distichum</i> (L.)) (Stahle, D.W. Cleaveland, M.K., (ITRDB))
PIEDMO	AD 1488	AD 2001	6.33	Piedmont Master Oak + Historical QUSP (Columbia unpubl)
WATVA	AD 1642	AD 1981	6.08	Watchdog Massenhutten Mountain (Columbia unpubl)
VA025	AD 1171	AD 1984	5.82	Nottoway River (World Data Bank) VA
WATCH	AD 1595	AD 1981	5.71	Hanover Tavern (Columbia unpubl)
VA009	AD1587	AD1982	5.37	Blue Ridge Parkway - Standard Virginia (Cook)
MKF	AD 1630	AD 1813	5.36	Middlekauf Farm, Kelly's Purchase, Sharpsburg. Maryland
ARC	AD 1570	AD 1844	5.25	Arcola Plantation, Loudoun Co.
HQFx1	AD 1630	AD 1836	5.19	Mount Fair, Albemarle County (Miles and Worthington 2008)
VA023	AD1372	AD1984	5.15	Dragon Run Standard Virginia bald cypress (<i>Taxodium distichum</i> (L.)) (Stahle, Cleaveland & He)
HQFx	AD 1571	AD 1872	4.74	Browns Cove Site Master (oak), Albemarle County (Miles and Worthington 2008)
HQFx2	AD 1643	AD 1815	4.72	Yates Schoolhouse (Demolished) Headquarters Farm Crozet Albemarle VA (Miles and Worthington 2008)
mtvx6	AD 1678	AD 1758	4.51	Mt Vernon Mansion (Oxford forthcoming)
SJC	AD 1556	AD 1849	4.49	St John's Church Richmond (Miles and Worthington in prep)

Table 2. Nøstodden ship timbers. The correlation between the average tree-ring curve Z179M002 and diverse chronologies for oak from North America (after Martin Bridge & Dan Miles pers comm). The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

- Nostodden, Norwegian Ship (Daly)
- South-Central PA Oak Chronology (Krusic and Cook, Griggs)
- Lancaster, PA, Schaeffer House (Griggs)
- Conococheague Institute (Griggs)

Fig 1. Nøstodden, Norway. Comparison of the average tree-ring curve from the Nøstodden timbers and a selection of North American chronologies (Carol Griggs pers comm).

As the dating of the tree-ring curves from the three timbers shows (fig. 2), the outermost preserved tree-ring is on sample 1 (Z179001a). With the new dating with the American material we can now determine that this outermost preserved tree-ring was formed in AD 1832. It is necessary to account for missing sapwood to estimate the felling date of the trees used. As mentioned above, only heartwood is preserved on the three samples, and we cannot know how much of the outer rings of the tree were trimmed in the shaping of these three ship frames. There are many species of oak in North America, and it has not been possible to identify these samples beyond genus level. Furthermore, the number of sapwood rings vary greatly in the American deciduous oaks, and as few as three sapwood rings is not unusual (Griggs pers comm). Therefore, the estimated felling date for the trees used to build the Nøstodden ship is placed at **after AD 1836** (indicated with green in fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Nøstodden, Norway. Diagram illustrating the dating of the timber from the ship. The result of the modelled calibration of the C14 dates from timber Z179002a is also shown. The estimated felling for the trees used to build the ship can be placed at after AD 1836.

Literature

Daly, A., 2016. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from the ship found at Nøstodden, Norway. Dendro.dk report 2016 : 74, Copenhagen.

Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Samples											
Z179001a	Norway Nøstodden 2 ship spant 1 QUSP	121	AD1712	AD1832	F	0	N	O	H1	1,62	after AD1836
Z179002a	Norway Nøstodden 2 ship spant 2 QUSP	154	AD1666	AD1819	V	0	N	O	H1	1,45	after AD1823
Z179003a	Norway Nøstodden 2 ship spant 2 QUSP	164	AD1651	AD1814	V	0	N	R	H1	1,35	after AD1818
Averages											
Z179M001	Norway Nøstodden 2 ship 2 timber QUSP	169	AD1651	AD1819						1,37	
Z179M002	Norway Nøstodden 2 ship 3 timber QUSP	182	AD1651	AD1832						1,35	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 - 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			13 March 2017								

When quoting these results please add the following:

in publication bibliography/literature lists:	Daly, Aoife, 2017. The dendrochronological dating of timbers from a ship found at Nøstodden, Norway. <i>dendro.dk report 2017:15</i> , Copenhagen.
In blogs and social media:	<i>dendro.dk report 2017:15</i>